

Dynamic Optimization in SDN-Enabled EONs with CV-QKD coexistence

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Abstract: This paper presents dynamic spectrum allocation strategies to mitigate noise impact on quantum channels, reduce blocking probability for quantum and classical channels, and optimize spectrum utilization leveraging an SDN architecture for integrating CV-QKD in EONs. © 2024 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

Elastic Optical Networks (EONs) are crucial for meeting the increasing demand for high-capacity, low-latency, and flexible optical transport networks. EONs offer flexible spectrum allocation, which ensures efficient use of bandwidth, enabling them to support on-demand provisioning of bandwidth adapted to dynamic traffic patterns.

The growing volume of sensitive information transmitted over optical networks necessitates robust security measures, as traditional encryption is vulnerable to quantum computer attacks. Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) provides a secure solution by using quantum physics principles to exchange encryption keys and detect eavesdropping. Continuous-variable QKD (CV-QKD) is a promising option that uses optical coherent technology, offering compatibility with the existing network infrastructure, and the possibility of achieving higher Secret Key Rate (SKR) and reducing implementation costs, even adopting commercial off-the-shelf components, with respect to other implementations [1, 2]. QKD systems require the *quantum* channel (QCh) for transmitting quantum states and the *public* interaction channel for classical communication between QKD nodes implemented for QKD post-processing, such as clock synchronization, estimation of parameters and key reconciliation [1]. Public and conventional classical *data* channels are referred collectively as classical channels (CCh). Integrating QKD into existing optical networks is challenging due to quantum signals being susceptible to noise from high-power CChs. While using dedicated dark fiber can shield QCh, it is expensive and scarce, making it impractical. Therefore, integrating weak quantum signals into existing fiber infrastructure with classical signals is more practical, reducing deployment costs and promoting sustainable quantum security. However, this coexistence is more challenging in EONs due to closely spaced frequency channels.

Research has demonstrated the coexistence of CV-QKD and classical communications within the same fiber in point-to-point links [2–4]. These works typically assess the impact of CCh power on CV-QKD performance by evaluating the achievable transmission distance and SKR under different scenarios. They often involve adjusting parameters like the quantum channel’s spectral position, guard band size, and CCh power to optimize both the CV-QKD performance (in terms of SKR) and the quality of transmission (QoT) of classical signals (in terms of BER) [4]. These findings provide practical guidelines and power bounds for efficient and secure coexistence of CV-QKD and traditional communications. However, few studies address networking aspects and algorithm development for QCh and CCh spectrum allocation in complex network scenarios and EON.

This work enhances the integration of CV-QKD and classical communications in EONs by exploring dynamic spectrum allocation strategies using an SDN architecture. Specifically, this paper proposes and evaluates rerouting strategies, to optimize spectrum utilization and reduce blocking probability (BP) for both QChs and CChs. Additionally, a simulated scenario with a single QCh and 51 CChs over a 20 km single-mode fiber (SMF) is used to determine an acceptable power limit for CChs.

2. System Model

Fig. 1 a) outlines a Software-Defined Networking (SDN) architecture for the integrated control of QKD and classical optical networks [2]. This architecture includes several key network components that interplay to establish and manage secure communication, which are briefly described below. In the application plane, **Cryptographic App** represents the end users of the secure communication services provided by the integrated network. In the control plane, **SD-QKD network controllers** (SDQ-C) manage QKD networks, while **SD-Optical controllers** (SDO-C) oversee optical networks. These controllers can either operate as separate entities that collaborate via an SDN Orchestrator or be integrated into a single SDN controller capable of orchestrating the interplay between QKD and classical network components. In the QKD plane, **QKD nodes** are the fundamental units responsible for generating and distributing quantum keys. These nodes typically consist of the following elements: Physical

QKD Device (including QKD modules), Key Manager (KM) and SDN Agent. In the optical plane, the **optical network** provides the physical transport infrastructure for both quantum and classical signals. The architecture envisions the use of reconfigurable optical add-drop multiplexers (ROADMs) to dynamically establish and manage both QChs and CChs between QKD nodes. In this work, the optical network topology consists of a set of ROADMs interconnected by dual-fiber links operating in the C-Band, where the total spectrum is divided into 320 frequency slots (FS), each with a bandwidth of 12.5 GHz. This configuration allows flexible allocation of spectrum to accommodate both QChs and CChs.

Fig. 1. a) SDN Architecture, b) Key pair provisioning workflow

The process, depicted in Fig. 1 b), for providing Cryptographic Apps with key pairs for secure communication is triggered when an App initiates a request to the SDQ-C to establish a secure communication channel with another App. This request triggers the SDN controllers to begin the process of allocating necessary resources and configuring the network. The SDQ-C determine the availability of QKD resources and interacts with the SDO-C to dynamically configure a lightpath for the QCh and associated CCh. This includes allocating optical spectrum and setting up power levels. Then the QKD nodes establish a QKD link and the generated keys are securely transferred between QKD nodes. Finally, the KM of the QKD nodes securely delivers the appropriate keys to the Apps.

The traffic model for the coexistence scenario considers a set of requests R , each request $r(s, d, b, q, l)$ is characterized by parameters such as source node s and destination node d , the number of FS b required for the CCh, a binary variable indicating the quantum security requirement q to encrypt the classical traffic. In the case of requests demanding quantum security, l denotes the required security level. To ensure data security, secret keys have a limited lifespan and must be renewed periodically. The key updating periods are determined by l .

2.1. Spectrum Allocation Optimization

To mitigate the negative impact of noise sources on QCh and maximize SKR, we propose allocating the QChs at higher frequencies within the C-band. This strategy exploits the fact that spontaneous Raman scattering, which is the dominant source of noise in the presence of sufficient guard band, has lower peak at frequencies above the classical signal [1, 3]. In scenarios where the higher-frequency spectrum is already occupied by CChs, these CChs will be rearranged to a different part of the spectrum. This rearrangement will be performed by the SDO-C, which has a global view and real-time knowledge of the current state of the optical resources. This rearrangement of active CChs involves: (1) releasing the required spectrum currently used by the CChs, and (2) computing alternative lightpaths with sufficient spectrum resources for the CChs. However, this rearrangement may also result in cases where it is not possible to reroute CChs by alternative lightpaths. In such cases, a priority policy can be defined. This policy determines whether the QCh is blocked if rerouting active CChs is impossible (**Rerouting-CCh priority**), or if the QCh is given higher priority, the active CChs are removed before their lifetime ends to ensure the QCh can be established (**Rerouting-QCh priority**). This process ensures that either the CChs or QChs can be allocated depending on the network conditions and predefined priority policies.

3. Simulations and Results

The simulation is conducted on a metro network topology with 6 nodes and 8 links (Fig.2 c)), where links are sufficiently short ($\leq 20\text{Km}$) to guarantee reliable transmission of quantum signals. Connection requests are dynamically generated following a Poisson distribution, with source and destination nodes randomly selected among all node pairs. Requests with quantum security requirements are limited to adjacent nodes. Each request requires 6 FSs for data transmission (i.e., data CChs). To mitigate noise effects and ensure appropriate spacing between CChs and QChs, 8 FS are reserved. The security level (l) for each request, randomly assigned from $\{1, 2, 3\}$, dictates key updating periods of $\{256, 128, 64\}$ ms for a 256 bit-sized quantum secret key. Therefore, a request requiring security will generate as many QKD connections (i.e., one QCh and one public CCh) as the key update period indicates. CChs are established following the k-shortest path routing and first-fit spectrum allocation (kSP-FF) algorithm with $k=4$, selecting the first path with enough contiguous FSs. QChs select one FS with the highest

index and reserve FSs for a guard band to spatially separate QChs from CChs.

One crucial aspect in coexistence scenario is identifying the optimal power levels that satisfy the requirements of both quantum signals (in terms of SKR) and classical signals (in terms of QoT). To assess the impact of CCh power on the performance of a QCh, a coexistence scenario involving a single QCh (at 195.95625 THz) and 51 CChs (ranging from 192.05625 - 195.80625 THz) over a 20 km SMF was simulated using VPIphotonics [5]. The test setup uses Gaussian-modulated coherent states (GMCS) CV-QKD protocol [4] at the transmitter. At the receiver, we perform phase-diversity detection with a 90-degree optical hybrid, followed by a parameter estimation step to calculate asymptotic SKR [3]. The spacing was 150 GHz between the QCh and the nearest CCh [2], and 75 GHz between individual CChs. Fig. 2 b) shows that the total CCh power should not exceed 8 dBm (-9.075 dBm/channel) to maintain a positive asymptotic SKR of ~ 104 kb/s, exceeding this level results in a negative SKR, preventing secure key generation. Besides, to check the feasibility of the lighpaths for CChs, GNPY was integrated as a QoT estimator tool in our simulations.

Fig. 2. a) Spectrum Utilization and BP, b) Effects of CChs Power on SKR, c) Metro Topology

Three spectrum allocation strategies were evaluated based on spectrum utilization and BP for QChs and CChs: **Rerouting-CCh priority**, **Rerouting-QCh priority**, and **No Rerouting** strategy that represents a baseline scenario where arriving requests are assigned spectrum resources if available, otherwise, they are blocked. The results, depicted in Fig. 2 a), show that both rerouting strategies, significantly outperform the No Rerouting by reducing BP for both CCh and QCh requests across all simulated traffic loads. For example, BP CCh lowers from 26.4% (No Rerouting) to 19.4% (Rerouting-CCh) and 8.1% (Rerouting-QCh) under 400 Er. Rerouting-QCh exhibits even better performance in terms of BP compared to Rerouting-CCh. It eliminates completely QChs blocking and reduces CChs blocking by dropping active CChs when no alternative lightpaths are available, releasing spectrum resources. However, it's crucial to acknowledge that this improvement comes at the cost of terminating ongoing CChs, which could impact the quality of service for classical communications. Similarly, both rerouting strategies optimize spectrum utilization. The rerouting techniques effectively act as reactive defragmentation mechanisms for the spectrum, offering more blocks of continuous spectrum available. Rerouting-QCh priority demonstrates a marginally higher spectrum utilization. This is because more CCh and QCh request are allocated.

4. Conclusions

This paper demonstrates that rerouting strategies optimize spectrum utilization and reduce BP for both QCh and CCh in EONs. This approach, facilitated by an SDN architecture, allows for dynamic spectrum allocation to minimize the impact of noise on QChs. A simulated coexistence scenario of CV-QKD revealed that the total power for CChs should not exceed 8 dBm to maintain a positive SKR. The findings underscore the potential of integrating CV-QKD with existing optical networks to enable secure and efficient future networks.

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